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A CREEP MODEL FOR THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID BI-STABLE LAMINATE

Yanqi Li, Fuhong Dai, Heng Li

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Introduction

Concept:

Anti-symmetric bistable laminate

Twisted bistable laminate

Symmetric bistable laminate

(1) Possess two stable states

(2) Achieve large deformation by transforming between two stable states

(3) Energy is only needed to actuate it, without continuous energy supply

Applications:

Bi-stable morphing winglet, Weaver, P., etc. 2007

Energy Harvesting, Arrieta, A., etc. 2010

Pattern Reconfigurable Antenna

FEA Method

Software: ABAQUS

Configuration A

Configuration B

Experiment

- The size of each laminate is 300mm×70mm with a stacking sequence of $[0_2/Al/90_2]_T$.
- The fatigue experiments are set up by a simple device that is designed for bi-stable fatigue test in motor driver and crank slider, loading frequency 1Hz.
- The plates are always placed in configuration B in creep experiments and the change of critical load is recorded with time.

The device of fatigue test

Creep experiment

Results and Discussion

The result of fatigue experiment

The result of creep experiment

- The critical load of bi-stable laminate gradually decreases with the increase of cycle index, and the decline of the critical load is mainly concentrated in the initial time.
- The drop of critical load is 1.042N, and reduces 39.95% on the basis of the original.

- The critical load drops from 2.610N to 1.575N at creep test, and decays 1.035N.

The change for critical load with time

The critical load contrast between fatigue test and creep test

- The finite element values and experimental values are close, and the trend and velocity of two curves decline are essentially the same.

- The drop speed of critical load at fatigue test significantly is faster than creep test.